

From NR to 6G in Unlicensed Spectrum: the RAT for Wireless Private Networks in Industry 4.0

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Abstract—Future smart factories require a privately-owned and wirelessly-connected network to accommodate diverse mobile devices and meet a variety of stringent requirements. Unlicensed spectrum is attracting a lot of interest for industrial wireless private networks due to its relatively ease of access and because it allows removing dependency on public networks. In this paper, we analyze the applicability of New Radio and 6G-based access to unlicensed spectrum (NR-U and 6G-U) as the Radio Access Technology (RAT) for Industry 4.0 scenarios.

I. INTRODUCTION

We are undoubtedly witnessing the transition into the 4-th industrial revolution, also termed Industry 4.0 or industrial Internet-of-Things (IIoT) [1]. Industry 4.0 focuses on integrating IoT and cyber-physical systems to the industrial automation domain with the main objective of driving the productivity of industrial automation verticals such as manufacturing, energy, utility, oil and gas refineries, and transportation. Communication for connected industries and automation demands stringent requirements in terms of high availability, high reliability, low latency, high security, high integrity, high maintainability, and, in some cases, high-accuracy positioning. Such critical communications in the Industry 4.0 generate an opportunity for the cellular industry [2], primarily driven by the interest of the industry verticals that need flexibility to accommodate mobile robots, automated guided vehicles, and head mounted displays with advanced mobile applications for workers (e.g., extended reality (XR) devices). In this regard, the investigation of 5G and beyond provides a significant opportunity for the future smart factories, to conform a privately-owned and wirelessly-connected network (i.e., a Wireless Private Network, WPN) for the Industry 4.0.

Unlicensed spectrum is expected to play a key role in future cellular networks due to its large global availability and relatively ease of access [3]. It enables cellular networks to expand its applicability beyond the usual licensed paradigm, as confirmed by latest 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) standard specifications, which started with 4G LTE Licensed-Assisted Access (LAA), MulteFire, and recently through 5G New Radio-based access to unlicensed spectrum (NR-U) [4]. NR-U will be included in future 3GPP specifications thanks to a Rel-16 Work Item that has been just approved. In particular, NR-U in its standalone mode (i.e., not anchored to a licensed carrier, contrary to the case of LAA) is attracting a lot of interest for industrial WPNs since it allows removing dependency on public networks.

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Industrial devices	latency (ms)	availability (%)	throughput (bps)	number
Industrial robot (control)	<1	>99.9999	10^3	>100
Mobile robot (control, XR)	<1	>99.9999	10^6	>100
Sensor (monitoring)	~100	>99.99	10^3	>200
Head mounted display (XR)	<10	>99.9999	10^9-10^6	>50
Handheld terminal (safety)	<10	>99.9999	10^6-10^3	>50
Automated guided vehicle	<10	>99.9999	10^6	>10
Security camera	~100	>99.99	10^9-10^6	>10

TABLE I: Requirements of selected Industry 4.0 devices.

In this short paper, we analyze the applicability of NR-U and its future evolution (termed in this paper as 6G-U) as the RAT to conform a WPN for Industry 4.0 scenarios. We review the requirements of selected industrial devices, and then identify the challenges and further improvements that are needed to apply 5G NR-U and 6G-U to operate in unlicensed spectrum while conforming a WPN and satisfying a variety of Industry 4.0 requirements. Our view for it incorporates network slicing, unlicensed/shared/licensed paradigms, multi-band operation, advanced multi-band and multi-beam selection algorithms, distributed computing, and distributed Machine Learning (ML) as key technology components for 6G-U.

II. INDUSTRY 4.0 REQUIREMENTS: SETTING THE CHALLENGES FOR FUTURE CELLULAR NETWORKS

In Table I, we illustrate the requirements of different Industry 4.0 devices that may coexist in a future smart factory, in terms of latency, availability, throughput, and number of devices. As it can be observed, the different devices can be classified as a combination of: latency-critical, availability-critical, throughput-critical, and massive-critical.

5G promises to fulfill some of the requirements for connectivity in industrial control and automation systems, such as high reliability and low latency, as well as to support mobility for robotics and machines. As compared to 4G LTE, the new opportunities that 5G NR access technology offers for the Industry 4.0 are: ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) for use cases like XR, connectivity for massive machine type communications (mMTC), Time Sensitive Networks (TSN) and Ethernet replacement, and expansion to unlicensed spectrum.

In particular, 3GPP NR has concentrated efforts into defining three main slice categories: eMBB, URLLC, and mMTC. However, we believe that in future 6G cellular networks for the Industry 4.0, ultra-reliable communications (URC) and low-latency communications (LLC) should be separated, and much more slice categories need to be defined by using two or more combinations of the 5G NR categories, e.g., eMBB and LLC. A key challenge is how to address simultaneously

Fig. 1: Challenges for WPNs.

the variety of connections/devices with different requirements in the future smart factories.

Some critical aspects of industrial WPNs are not addressed in 5G yet, and will need to be considered in 6G. Among them: *i)* security and privacy, *ii)* latency below 1 ms, *iii)* resilience for massive deployments, *iv)* three intrinsic challenges of WPNs that are shown in Fig. 1 and include 1) deployment and management of multiple spatially-located WPNs, 2) resilience against external unintentional interference, and 3) resilience against external intentional jamming.

III. 6G-U AND ITS APPLICABILITY TO INDUSTRY 4.0

Differently from LAA and MulteFire technologies that were specifically designed to operate in the 5 GHz band, NR-U and 6G-U should consider multiple bands that have been recently opened for unlicensed operations. They include: 2.4 GHz band (unlicensed worldwide), 3.5 GHz band (shared in the US), 5 GHz band (unlicensed worldwide), 6 GHz band (unlicensed in the US and Europe), 37 GHz band (shared in the US), and 60 GHz band (unlicensed worldwide). First efforts in the NR-U standardization are focusing on sub 6 GHz bands [4], but millimeter-wave (mmWave) bands will be later addressed or maybe left for 6G-U. Further efforts will later focus on even higher bandwidths, as available in the 90-100 GHz band, and of course at the Terahertz (THz) level.

Also, differently from LAA and MulteFire that were specifically designed under carrier aggregation and standalone modes, respectively, NR-U considers different deployment scenarios that include: carrier aggregation, dual connectivity, and standalone modes [4]. 6G-U will likely expand the deployment scenarios by considering more than two bands for carrier aggregation and dual connectivity, as well as aggregation/connectivity with multiple unlicensed bands (sub 6 GHz, mmWave, and THz) as a way to enable a new **multi-band standalone deployment scenario uniquely in unlicensed**.

The NR-U and 6G-U systems should be flexible enough not only to support the different bands and deployment scenarios but also to follow the region- and band-specific regulatory requirements to gracefully coexist with other stakeholders in the unlicensed spectrum (e.g., Wi-Fi). As such, to meet worldwide regulation, a Listen-Before-Talk (LBT)-based access procedure needs to be incorporated. *LBT usage partially covers the challenges of WPNs shown in Fig. 1* [5]. As a downside, it may increase the access delay, and so the total latency.

The pillars for 6G-U to be applied in future smart factories that we envision include:

- multi-band operation through the integration of sub 6 GHz, mmWave, and THz bands at the radio access network to improve reliability, availability, and resilience.

Fig. 2: Integration of RAN slicing, multi-band operation, multi-spectrum sharing paradigms, and ML-assisted network control in Industry 4.0.

- network slicing to meet simultaneously the requirements of latency-critical, availability-critical, throughput-critical, and massive-critical devices.
- distributed computing and network control to increase the quality, accuracy and precision of industrial processes.
- enhanced URLLC to address low-latency, high-secure and high-reliable communications, including TSN, packet duplication, and multi-connectivity.

All these pillars require the support for a **ML-assisted network control** in charge of managing, through software-based platforms, the complexity of the network in an autonomous manner. A data-centric approach needs to be supported to collect information through sensors in the smart factory, while distributed actuators execute actions taken by distributed and/or centralized controllers. The challenges to address are multiple, like the automatic selection of the most appropriate band and/or technology to meet the wide variety of requirements; the stability of multiple distributed learning controllers making decisions that can interact among each other; the timeliness of the autonomous decisions and learning processes, in a scenario where latency is such a stringent requirement. This paves the way for cross-disciplinary areas of research, where communication and robotics experts have to interact to provide novel connected industrial scenarios.

The integration of the different pillars is shown in Fig. 2. In this framework, it is key: *i)* to develop the theoretical foundations for licensed, unlicensed and shared spectrum paradigms, *ii)* to design multi-band and multi-beam selection algorithms, using optimization methods and/or ML algorithms, *iii)* to derive methods for RAN slicing by considering the multi-band and multi-spectrum sharing opportunities, *iv)* to develop distributed computing for edge network services and control systems for industrial automation, *v)* to design distributed ML-based algorithms for network control that may exploit distributed data bases and distributed computing resources, and *vi)* to study the impact of LBT on the latency performance and investigate how to meet stringent LLC requirements.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Chen *et al.*, "Smart factory of industry 4.0: Key technologies, application case, and challenges," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, Dec. 2017.
- [2] 3GPP TR 22.804, *Study on Communication for Automation in Vertical domains (CAV) (Release 15)*, v16.1.0, Sep. 2018.
- [3] R. Zhan *et al.*, "LTE-unlicensed: the future of spectrum aggregation for cellular networks," *IEEE Wireless Commun.*, vol. 22, no. 3.
- [4] 3GPP TR 38.889, *Study on NR-based access to unlicensed spectrum (Release 15)*, v16.0.0, Dec. 2018.
- [5] S. Lagen and L. Giupponi, "Listen before receive for coexistence in unlicensed mmWave bands," *IEEE WCNC*, Apr. 2018.